

WHO IS THE "LAST VICTIM OF THE WAR"?

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Annotation: *Each of the works of Utkir Hoshimov, one of the great representatives of Uzbek literature, is a great gift to our literature.*

The story of "The Last Victim of the War" reveals the same aspect: the writer talks to the reader about his duties and responsibilities.

This article tells the story of one of the important scenes of this story that can lead to different approaches.

Keywords: *war theme, unconventional approach, "Wrath style", period tragedy, domestic problem.*

It is possible to draw different conclusions from each case. Basically, the first conclusions in a matter are like an early fruit - you regret it. But these regrets help to educate and develop a person. neither the flavor nor the benefit of the puzzle counts.

The story of "The Last Victim of the War" is one of those works that requires an unusual approach from the reader. even. But ... what if what we think isn't what we know ?!

At the textile mill, the mechanic-Shoikrom was not recruited for the war. "He was married shortly before the war began. There was a war and times changed."

Shoikrom is hardworking, family-oriented, responsible and patient.

The reader puts himself in the shoes of a young mechanic and immediately becomes sympathetic to him, begins to understand him, assesses everything as normal. The story is like a shot fired when the kick is pressed. No, anyway, there is a conclusion that it is better than the consequences. A person who suffers from a great tragedy easily accepts small losses.

Shoikrom is a complex image. The reader is annoyed by his support, wondering if I did the right thing! However, there are other aspects in which the involuntary student "runs away" from the electrician:

- 1) Though the times are hard, his thoughts of "Shut up!" shows;
- 2) "submissive" to the whims of his wife Khadija, the yard left by the father will be with a cotton wall in the middle;

3) He doesn't notice that his mother's fingers are cracked. Isn't it natural for a boy who works day and night not to notice it? , from the beginning it can be assessed that he became more indifferent to the pains and condition of his parents;

4) Shoikrom came home late from work. Aunt Umri, her mother, came in from the yard behind the wall "like a ghost" (that is, very thin and weak). The son tells his wife to bring food to his mother. His wife's long yellow face turns red and he says, "No way."

5) Standing in a yard and suffering from tuberculosis for ten days, he does not know about the condition of his brother Shone'mat, who is "clinging to the ground". True, he regrets it, sighs. He who says he will do good will not have time to do good. " It must be done, vassal!

6) He said to his wife, "Cursed be your father! If you lead a cow under your nose, you will be stunned."

7) He admits that his wife's opinion is more reasonable than his own, that his wife is tough. does not speak, "he admits;

8) When he throws electric wires into a strawberry-planted bush, he warns his wife and children of this danger and tells his mother behind the wall nothing about the "trap."

With these "accusations", it would be wrong to put Shoikrom on a bad horse. No one denies this. However, the hardships of the times and the hardships of life should not serve as a ticket for a person to travel to the world of mistakes.

In the repeated sentences of the story, the knot of events is untied. In this sentence, the mother's service is over. He needs help. The "mountain" the mother believed in shouted "Shouldn't she shoot me if she told me to!" if he walks! The events of the work swell towards the necessity of tragedy. As she was leaving the cemetery, Shoikrom heard people say, "The war is over, did you hear? This news is supposed to be the heaviest in the" punishment code "read on Shoikrom." The death of the mother, who remained in a state of spiritual acceptance, is a unique lesson for the growth of Shoikrom, a symbol of the hammer struck on the head ". Everywhere-holiday, in his house-burial! The young man, who had tied his waist tightly for labor until his mother's death, will now tie his waist at the funeral. Involuntarily you want to call him "the last victim of the war."

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